

A non-Egyptian «Egyptian» stone vessel from Ras Al Jinz RJ-2, Sultanate of Oman: Critical review of an entrenched hypothesis

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*Posséder la connaissance ne tue pas le sens
du merveilleux et du mystère. Il y a toujours
un mystère au-delà (Anaïs Nin). À Serge*

Abstract: This short communication aims to re-discuss the proposed provenance of a reworked stone vessel fragment from the Early Bronze Age site Ras Al Jinz RJ-2 along the coast of central Oman. In the original publication (Cleuziou and Tosi, 2000), it was linked with Egypt thus becoming the first and sole known connection between the Umm an-Nar communities of south-eastern Arabia and late Old Kingdom's Egypt. However, a reappraisal of the mineralogical texture of the stone used to manufacture the object seems to confidently exclude an Egyptian origin. Other possible sources are therefore discussed.

Keywords: Oman; Egypt; Indus Valley; Bronze Age; fossiliferous limestone.

The ultimate goal of this note is to provide some constructive considerations about the geographical and cultural origin of a unique reworked stone vessel fragment (DA12729 in the recording system of the Ministry of Heritage and Tourism of Oman) found in Building X (Room 15) of the Early Bronze Age site RJ-2 at Ras Al Jinz (ca. 2500–2000 BCE), along the coast of central Oman in south-eastern Arabia (Figure 1).

Ras Al Jinz RJ-2, Sultanate of Oman

Extensive excavations by the French–Italian Joint Hadd Project in the bay of Ras Al Jinz provided unique evidence of a small coastal settlement playing a pivotal role in projecting the regional trade routes into the so-called Middle Asian Interaction Sphere. After sporadic Neolithic settlement in the fourth millennium BCE (Cleuziou and Tosi, 2000: 28), the Ras Al Jinz bay was seamlessly occupied in the following millennium (Azzarà, 2019). The two Early Bronze Age sites RJ-2 and RJ-3, in fact, likely formed a single settlement, while clusters of funerary stone cairns were built on the rocky terraces encompassing the bay. While the early third millennium BC levels are still being explored in RJ-3 (De Rorre et al., 2020), from 1985 to 2011 explorations in RJ-2 have exposed two main compounds of mud-brick buildings spanning the second half of the millennium (Cleuziou and Tosi, 2000) (Figure 2).

The Southern (Period II, c. 2500-2300 BCE) and Northern (Periods III & IV, c. 2300-2000 BCE) compounds, which cover almost half a hectare with a large central gap, were largely

altered and expanded during the different occupation phases, testifying to a dynamic socio-economic organisation (Azzarà and De Rorre, 2018) (Figure 3). All buildings were composed of small rectangular rooms showing low functional specialisation. In addition to food processing areas and storage facilities, several craft activities were also documented all over the site, including shell working for the production of small ornaments, copper processing for making everyday implements, and flint knapping for stone tools. However, the most significant characteristic of RJ-2 was its exceptional role as a trade hub linking the hinterland of south-eastern Arabia with overseas regions, including southern Mesopotamia and the greater Indus Valley. Flat copper ingots, Umm an-Nar type softstone and pottery vessels, the use of frankincense, and agricultural products such as dates and jujubes indicate interaction with interior oases for either local uses or export (Cleuziou and Tosi, 2000; Costantini and Audisio, 2001). On the other side, imports comprise a wide range of tools and commodities mainly from the greater Indus Valley, including copper stamp seals, carnelian and elephant ivory ornaments, tall painted jars, and large storage containers; links with Mesopotamia are witnessed by a few pottery containers and several hundred bitumen slabs likely from the coating of a reed-built sea-going vessel of the type mentioned in several cuneiform texts from Girsu and Lagash (Zarins, 2008; Laursen and Steinkeller, 2017: 107–109; Badel, 2020; Vosmer, 2020).

Stone Vessel Fragment (DA12729)

In this framework, the discovery in Building X (Room 15) of a reworked stone vessel fragment (DA12729) deserves further attention. According to the excavators, Serge Cleuziou and Maurizio Tosi, there was nothing suggesting any specialised function for Building X, which was dated around 2200 BCE based on the material culture and the general stratigraphy of the site (Cleuziou and Tosi, 2000: 36). However, the discovery in Room 16 of a necklace (DA12849) composed of tiny faience and silver beads strung along with a single long carnelian bead, which were likely imported from the greater Indus Valley (Kenoyer, 2017; Kenoyer and Frenez, 2018), could indicate that it may have been occupied by a socio-economic entity that had access to exotic items imported from overseas regions. The discovery in the same building of the reworked stone vessel fragment (DA12729) discussed in this paper may further strengthen this interpretation.

DA12729 was described by Cleuziou and Tosi (2000: 36 and fig. 11.3) as “the flaring bottom of a cylindrical vessel made from red-and-white conglomerate stone, very likely of Egyptian origin” (Figure 4). This object is presently exhibited in the National Museum of Oman, Muscat, with the same description. However, Cleuziou and Tosi never explained their reasoning for attributing the provenance of stone vessel fragment DA12729 to Egypt, nor did they provide references to comparable objects as support for their interpretation.

The significance of this specific cultural and geographical attribution is not trivial. In the second half of the third millennium BCE, south-eastern Arabia – named “Magan” in the Mesopotamian cuneiform texts – was an active component of the large network of mutual interactions and exchanges known as the Middle Asian Interaction Sphere (Possehl, 2007), which stretched from the Indus Valley to the Levant and from southern Arabia to Central Asia. If we were to include the reworked stone vessel DA12729 as an indication of contacts with Egypt, this would result in a totally new dimension of socio-cultural interaction. In fact, this reworked stone vessel would represent the only evidence for trade or exchange, either direct or

intermediated, between late Old Kingdom Egypt and the coeval Umm an-Nar communities of south-eastern Arabia. Otherwise, there are no other traces of interaction between these two regions until much later periods. According to Abedl M. Sayed (1989: 155), “there is no evidence throughout Pharaonic history for any direct maritime relationship (meaning that either the Egyptians sailed across the Red Sea to contact the Arabians, or vice versa) before the Ptolemaic period”. The scaraboid amulet-seals of likely Levantine or local production recently found in northern Oman/UAE and on Failaka Island now date the beginning of tenuous Egyptian stylistic influences over the greater Gulf region to the last centuries of the second millennium BCE (Frenez et al. 2021: 10 and fig. 5; Mahfouz et al. 2021).

A careful re-examination of the reworked stone vessel fragment (DA12729) provides new clues regarding the inaccuracies in its original mineralogical characterization and consequently its possible provenance. According to Cleuziou and Tosi (2000: 36), DA12729 was made from a “conglomerate stone”, which is typical of some types of Egyptian stone vessels (Lilyquist, 1995: 12-13). However, this identification is not correct. The vessel fragment found at Ras Al Jinz RJ-2, in fact, is evidently made from a fossiliferous limestone showing white-yellowish fossils embedded in a red-brown matrix (Figure 4). According to benthic foraminifera palaeontologist Johannes Pignatti, Department of Earth Sciences at Sapienza University of Rome, based on the available images “it would seem that the organogenic portion of the rock is represented by thalli of calcareous coralline algae of the order Corallinales, possibly belonging in the family Corallinaceae, showing in places irregular dichotomous branches” (pers. communication, Feb. 15th 2021).

Several types of fossiliferous limestone have been reported in Oman, but a careful review of the related literature (Guba, 2007; Hoffmann et al. 2016; Al-Kindi, 2018; Searle, 2019), and targeted field-surveys (Guba, pers. communication, Jan. 27th 2012; Hoffmann, pers. communication, Aug 15th 2016; Law and Frenez, 2012) did not reveal the presence of any stone with this specific matrix. Additional research for this type of stone was undertaken by examining stone vessels and other objects in published catalogues and websites of leading museums with large Egyptian and Near Eastern collections, i.e. the Louvre Museum, the British Museum, the Metropolitan Museum of Art, Brooklyn Museum, etc. After finding no comparable examples, I contacted James A. Harrell, Prof. Emeritus of Geology at the Department of Environmental Sciences, University of Toledo, whose research focuses on the archaeological geology of ancient Egypt (Harrell, 2021). According to Harrell (pers. communication, Sept. 10th 2016):

“The stone used for the Ras Al Jinz vessel is not from Egypt. The white to pale green areas look like animals burrows, which are commonly referred to as ‘trace fossils’. There are certainly sedimentary rocks in Egypt with similar trace fossils but not with the same overall appearance. In any case, I have never encountered any of these rocks used for vessels or anything else in Egypt.”

My current impression is that Cleuziou and Tosi misunderstood this artefact for an Egyptian jar made from a porphyry like andesite, dolerite or trachyandesite (Figure 5A), or a red-in-white limestone breccia that is also often imitated on clay vessels purposely painted to resemble elite stone vessels (Figure 5B). In particular, this latter vessel type, on which the applied painting

technique rounded the sharp angles of the simulated mineral inclusions, looks so similar to the stone used for making DA12729 (but with inverted colours) that even experienced scholars like Cleuziou and Tosi may have been deceived after a cursory glance.

Based on the lack of any comparable stone in Egypt, we should consider excluding an Egyptian origin for the Ras Al Jinz “Egyptian” vessel DA12729, and look instead for a different cultural and geographical provenance. Massimo Vidale, Prof. of Near Eastern Archaeology at the University of Padua (pers. communication, Feb. 15th 2021), who has considerable experience in the geoarchaeological study of fossiliferous limestones in Iran (Desset et al. 2016), never encountered a stone similar to that used to manufacture the Ras Al Jinz fragment on the Iranian Plateau. This hypothesis was also confirmed by Daniel T. Potts (pers. communication, Oct. 10th 2016).

Another region that needs to be considered is the Indus Valley, where there are at least three major areas that produce a similar type of yellow-in-brown fossiliferous limestone, the so-called Sang-e-Maryam (Stone of Mary), which is very similar to but still not identical to that used for DA12729. According to Randall W. Law (2011: 79-80 and fig. 4.6), this type of rock is presently found from Sangjani in the Rawalpindi District of Punjab, Pakistan, near the town of Habur in the Jaisalmer District of Rajasthan, India. Sang-e-Maryam was also worked at several Indus Civilization sites, including Dholavira in the Great Rann of Kutch of western Gujarat, India, and Harappa in Punjab, Pakistan (Law, 2011: 79 and fig. 4.6; Bisht, 2015: 598 and fig. 8.316, 754 and fig. 11.4) (Figure 6).

In south-eastern Arabia, a local white-in-black fossiliferous limestone called Waagenophillum, which originates from outcrops on the Jabal Al Akhdar in Oman, had some appeal from the Late Neolithic to the Iron Age. However, its discovery at archaeological sites is extremely rare and is mainly witnessed by the intentional collection of unworked, heavily rounded pebbles from deep seasonal streams descending from the Jabal Al Akhdar (Law and Frenez, 2012; Jean et al. 2018: 137, note 11; Degli Esposti and Tagliamonte, 2020) (Figure 7). Despite the long, renowned tradition in the manufacturing of soft-stone vessels from chlorites (David-Cuny, 2002a, 2002b, 2011; Harrower et al. 2016), a local Omani origin for DA12729 seems also to be excluded at the moment.

Conclusions

To conclude, this note hopefully demonstrates that the origin of the reworked stone vessel fragment DA12729 is far from being proven. Still, the alleged Egyptian origin proposed by Cleuziou and Tosi seems to be confidently dismissed. Despite the lack of a positive geological matching to date, considering the robust evidence for direct trade links between Indus Civilization sites and Ras Al Jinz RJ-2 (Cleuziou and Tosi, 2000; Gogte, 2000; Frenez, 2020a, 2020b, 2021), and the manufacturing of stone vessels from a similar fossiliferous limestone documented at Dholavira and Harappa, the greater Indus Valley is presently the most plausible candidate for the provenance of DA12729. However, this working hypothesis is yet to be tested with a rigorous multidisciplinary approach. In addition to a new documentation using digital microscopy, complementary non-destructive geochemical analyses of the stone composing DA12729 should also be ideally performed to allow future identification of its geological source and possibly establish if intentional heat treatments may have altered the original matrix and colours.

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Figures

Figure 1. Map of the Sultanate of Oman with indication of the sites and locations mentioned in the text (basemap by GinkgoMaps Project).

Figure 2. Ras Al Jinz bay (Oman). Main landscape features and archaeological sites (modified after Azzarà and De Rorre, 2018: fig. 1).

Figure 3. Ras Al Jinz RJ-2 (Oman). Plan of the Umm an-Nar settlement with indication of the discovery context of DA12729 (in red) (modified after Azzarà, 2019: fig. 4).

Figure 4. Ras Al Jinz RJ-2 (Oman). Reworked stone vessel base fragment DA12729 (photograph D. Frenez, drawing after Cleuziou and Tosi, 2000: fig. 11.3).

Figure 5. A) Egyptian lug handles jar made from porphyritic rock (courtesy Metropolitan Museum of Art); B) Egyptian funerary vessel painted to imitate stone (courtesy Brooklyn Museum); trachyandesite porphyry from Wadi Umm Towat in Egypt (bottom left) and red-and-white limestone breccia from El-Issawia Sharq in Egypt (bottom right) (courtesy J.A. Harrell).

Figure 6. Dholavira, Gujarat (India). Fragment of a dish made from Sang-e-Maryam (Stone of Mary) fossiliferous limestone (Bisht, 2015: fig. 8.316).

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Figure 7. Unworked pebbles of a white-in-black fossiliferous limestone (*Waagenophillum*) from the Sultanate of Oman: (A) Neolithic site RH-6 in Ras Al Hamra, Muscat (photograph by D. Frenez), (B) Early Bronze Age stone tower ST1, Salut (courtesy Italian Mission to Oman), (C) Early Iron Age ritual building in Mudhmar East, Adam (courtesy French Archaeological Mission in Central Oman); (D) Outcrops on the Jabal Al Akhdar (photograph by D. Frenez).